

Computers as Partners: A Technology Forecast for Decision-making in the 21st Century

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Abstract

By the end of the next decade, computers will not be just information gatherers who return reams of keyword-related information. Instead computers will become mobile intelligent helpers who will truly understand entire problems and provide just the right information to solve them. What capabilities will be needed to realize such advanced systems? This Technology Forecast Panel will project technology advances and assess the impact such systems might have on future decision-makers. The scenarios and ideas presented by the panelists will provide a reasonable starting point for discussion and solicitation of alternative views.

Panel Members:

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Dr. Eloise Coupey	Virginia Tech
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1. Introduction

Computers have never been cheaper or faster. One can argue that we have reached the point where computers serve as dedicated servants. They have been transformed from being difficult to use, data and text-processing machines to voice and video multimedia devices where just about any information is at your fingertips.

Despite all this capability, information systems usually support a single person on only a single piece of a larger problem. The real breakthrough awaits us in the next century when we make computers our partners instead of simple servants who need to be directed at every step of the way. Computers will not be just information gatherers who return reams of keyword-related information. Instead computers will become mobile intelligent helpers who will truly understand entire problems and provide not only the right information but also knowledge to help reach final solutions. In achieving this goal, computers will naturally participate with and coordinate groups of people in all the phases of dynamic decision making, from gathering necessary information to devising

alternatives, selecting the best choice and communicating decisions across the organization.

2. Where we are today

Today's decision maker is caught in the middle between increasingly complex problem domains and a vast world of digitized information spread across a multitude of databases (i.e., web pages, knowledge bases, legacy databases, and data warehouses). Physical access to the data is no longer dictated by geography (the Internet has changed that). Logical constraints still hinder the decision maker from using that data due to conflicting protocols, data definition schemes and computer architectures. Getting the right information to the decision-maker still remains a serious problem.

Intelligent tools have proven to be helpful for the right problem but such stand-alone black boxes also have their limitations. Search states for even simple problems are too large to be handled in a timely fashion [1]. Simplifying assumptions used in the black box approach to model the external environment can easily become out-of-date as the world changes, rendering results obsolete.

Consequently, even though information systems abound and data seems only a mouse-click away, neither humans nor computers can effectively handle the knowledge work that is demanded of them.

Another shortfall in decision-making is that we have too often only mechanized existing tasks and forms without re-engineering the entire process. By limiting computers into doing only the same things that we used to do manually, we have not realized their great potential and may have only complicated our lives.

Its single task perspective and the necessity of human control limit the mechanization stage. Individual task orientation brings with it a tunnel vision that fails to bring the full power of a computer system to bear on the total problem. Since we use computer systems to handle only part of the greater mission (usually the portion that deals with well-structured problems and structured data),

the human is then required to fill in whatever tasks remain.

Humans are also required to decide which tools are needed for the task at hand, when and where to use them, and it is their responsibility to select and bring to bear the proper data to a set of disjointed tools and computer systems. Although we have made computers more user-friendly, it is still a daunting task to make this match of data and computer system. Consequently, productivity and effectiveness suffer.

3. Future Directions: Computers as Partners

New types of web-accessible intelligent information systems will become commonplace in the next decade. These systems will incorporate a mission-perspective and provide dynamic and immediate access to command and control information with maximum mobility.

These systems will leverage technology advances in critical areas such as intelligent browsing, intelligent active knowledge bases, problem solving, and natural language human-computer interaction. Knowledge workers will be supported as they address the big picture, not just as they handle the individual tasks. This requires a process orientation that shifts isolated pieces of the total solution to what really needs to be accomplished. New information infrastructures need to represent commonsense knowledge and incorporate that in inferential reasoning. A missing component of this knowledge layer has been the ontology that captures the millions of things the average person knows about the world. The next decade will see huge knowledge bases that provide this missing link [2].

4.1 User Interaction

The key interface between the decision maker and complex missions and large, complicated knowledge bases will be a customizable communication device. These will be small enough to travel with the decision maker and would use web-based technology and domain knowledge of the mission to gain access to the necessary information space and to interface to other components that correspond to the decision making process. It would be built upon a natural language, speech recognition and voice synthesis interface which can guide the human in matching data to program to problem solution.

4.2 Active Information Selection

Once the decision-maker has established his information needs, the system must be able to find and deliver that information in a form suitable for both human understanding and further computation. Current Internet technology has made computer delivery of data and information a normal occurrence. What remains to be

done, however, is the most important part of the information selection process: delivery of only the right information for the task at hand. Improved natural language processing tools will provide more precise extracting and abstracting of knowledge from heterogeneous information sources [3].

4.3 Dynamic Decision Making

Once information is at hand, the next step in the decision making process is devising alternatives. For example, in military applications, decision making is driven by demands within a large command and control infrastructure consisting of teams of people at different sites. When you factor in high-stress and time-sensitive operations, the demands placed on the decision-maker become enormous. Decision support tools should help provide decision structure driven by both the situation and the information to help reduce the pressure on a military commander.

There will be no need to be tied to a fixed location during the decision-making process either. Mobile agents will travel from machine to machine in a heterogeneous network under their own control, interacting with programs and data on different machines and returning home with a final result [4].

New decision support systems will provide script guidance to help a decision-maker follow a work-flow of possible actions. In addition to integrating information from different sources, a leader will make a decision with the input of a flexible team of people and will communicate the results back to the team [5].

5. References

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